

Dario Zagorec*, Jasmina Vagan

Ministarstvo poljoprivrede, Uprava za stručnu podršku razvoju poljoprivrede,
Ulica grada Vukovara 78, 10000 Zagreb, Hrvatska

*dario.zagorec@mps.hr

Sustavi mesnoga pašnoga govedarstva

Tijekom četiri godine i devet mjeseci 502 sudionika sudjelovala su na 17 demodogađanja održana na 22 poljoprivredna gospodarstva s temom mesnoga pašnoga govedarstva. Uprava za stručnu potporu razvoju poljoprivrede Ministarstva poljoprivrede partner je u provedbi projekta OBZOR 2020 nazvanim Projekt Nefertiti. Cilj je bio uspostaviti tematsku mrežu HUB 3 Ekološki sustavi u stočarstvu u Republici Hrvatskoj i povezati hrvatske poljoprivrednike u mrežu. Aktivnosti tijekom provedbe bile su usmjerene na razmjenu znanja i iskustava o specifičnostima ekološkog uzgoja stoke, omogućavajući prelazak konvencionalnih poljoprivrednika na ekološke, i to uz poboljšanje interakcije s potrošačima. S obzirom na to da su praktična iskustva u proizvodnom sustavu tova na pašnjacima vrlo skromna a potencijal golem, cilj je bio otkloniti predrasude i motivirati postojeće, potencijalne i mlade uzgajivače za stvaranje dodatne vrijednosti u upravljanju mešnim pašnim i ekološkim govedarstvom. Na kraju provedbe Projekta Nefertiti može se zaključiti da u Hrvatskoj postoji nekoliko različitih pristupa mesnom pašnom govedarstvu i različitih sustava, ovisno o zemljopisnim i klimatskim uvjetima. Sustav krava-tele najrašireniji je i bilježi zapažen rast. Proizvođači proizvodnju mogu povećati za 10-30 %, a poboljšanjem kvalitete paše, hranidbe i tehnologije rezultati mogu biti 30-50 % bolji. Farme koje uzgajaju krave za proizvodnju teladi uz tovljenje vlastita pomlatka mogu povećati svoje prihode prodajom govedine.

Ključne riječi: mesno govedarstvo, pašni tov, krava-tele, Nefertiti

Beef cattle grazing systems

In the period over four years and nine months, 502 participants attended 17 demo events organized within 22 agricultural holdings with topics of meat pasture cattle breeding. The Directorate for Professional Support for Agricultural Development of the Ministry of Agriculture is a partner in the implementation of the HORIZON 2020 project, entitled as the Nefertiti project. The goal was to establish a thematic network HUB 3 Robust organic livestock systems in the Republic of Croatia and to connect Croatian farmers in that network. The activities during the implementation were focused on the exchange of knowledge and experiences regarding the specifics of organic livestock breeding, enabling the transition of conventional farmers to organic farmers, while improving interaction with consumers. Considering that practical experiences in the production system of fattening on pasture are very modest and the potential is huge, the goal was to remove prejudices and motivate existing, potential and young breeders to create additional value in the management of meat pasture and organic cattle breeding. At the end of the implementation of the Nefertiti project, it can be concluded that in Croatia we have several different approaches to meat pasture cattle breeding and different systems, who depends on geographical and climatic conditions. The cow-calf system is the most widespread one and shows a noticeable growth. Producers can increase their production by 10-30 % and by improving the quality of pasture, feeding and technology, the results can be 30-50 % better. Farms that breed cows for calf production in addition to fattening their own calves can increase their income by selling meat.

Key words: pasture beef cattle breeding, pasture fattening, cow-calf, Nefertiti